

TABLE 3—COMPARATIVE KINETIC PARAMETERS FOR THE HYDROLYSIS OF PHENYL PHOSPHATE DIESTERS VIA THEIR NEUTRAL (1 M) AND CONJUGATE ACID SPECIES (4 M)

Phenyl phosphate diesters	Temp. °C	(5 + log K_e)	ΔE kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ e.u.	Fission	($\sigma + \sigma_I + V$) ^g
Phenyl ^b	100	1.84	20.8	27.96	P-O [†]	0.0
<i>p</i> -Cl ^o	80	3.12	10.6	65.00	P-O	0.454
<i>p</i> -Br ^d	98	1.82	20.14	30.00	P-O	0.464
2,4-di-Cl ^d	98	2.49	16.60	33.90	P-O	2.494
<i>p</i> -Cl-O-MeO ^o	98	1.97	18.21	36.61	P-O	1.774
2,4,6-tri-Cl ^f	90	2.67	24.41	11.87	P-O	4.534
2,4,6-tri-Br ^o	98	2.66	26.08	7.09	P-O	4.944
This work						
<i>p</i> -Cl-2,6-di-Me	98	0.38	27.36 [‡] 14.59 [‡]	15.42	P-O	-1.666
6-Br-2,4-di-Cl ^h	90	2.70	33.72	-13.71	P-O	4.734

^o σ = Hammett substituent constant, σ_I = Inductive substituent constant, V = Charton's steric substituent constant; (Ref. 14). ^bRef. 6. ^oRef. 16. ^dRef. 17. ^eRef. 19. ^fRef. 20. ^gRef. 21. ^hRef. 22. [†]Fission confirmed. [‡]At 4 M HCl. [‡]At 3 M HCl.

of two O—Me groups in each aryl system in the present case decreases the reactivity due to their 'ortho effect'. Unimolecular hydrolysis is also responsible for this decrease. Another reason for the decrease in reactivity is the orientation of the two aryl nuclei, which being symmetrical are opposed to each other and hence the overall effect is equal and opposite in magnitude.

This diester is taken to hydrolyse with P—O bond fission as it follows an isokinetic relationship¹⁵ (figure not shown) with other similarly substituted diaryl esters (Table 3) and gives a β value equal to 423.1 K. This value being greater than the absolute experimental temperature (371 K) shows that the reaction is most probably governed by the energy of activation. This is supported by a low value of acid-catalysed rates ($K_H^\ddagger = 0.0067$ mol dm⁻³ s⁻¹) too.

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Zinc Chloride Catalysed Condensation of Mesityl Oxide with Benzoylacetone

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BASE catalysed Michael condensations of β -diketones and β -ketoesters with α,β -unsaturated-carbonyl compounds are well known to yield products of the cyclohexenone type¹⁻¹⁰. It is further known that branching at α - and/or β -position of the α,β -unsaturated-carbonyl compounds inhibit Michael addition. Literature reveals that Michael condensation induced by acid catalysts has not attracted much attention as yet. This field, however, appears interesting specially for condensations involving highly alkylated α,β -unsaturated-carbonyl compounds.

Condensation of mesityl oxide with acetoacetic ester in the presence of Lewis acids, like BF_3 , Et_2O and anhydrous zinc chloride¹¹⁻¹³, was shown to yield cyclised products. More recently, one of us¹⁴ has reported the isolation of 6-acetyl-3,5,5-trimethylcyclohex-2-enone (1) and 4-acetyl-3,5,5-trimethylcyclohex-2-enone (2) from anhydrous zinc chloride catalysed condensation of mesityl oxide and acetylacetone. In order to examine the generality of such reaction, the work has been extended to the condensation of mesityl oxide and benzoylacetone in the presence of anhydrous zinc chloride. The condensation has also been carried out by replacing anhydrous zinc chloride with anhydrous aluminium chloride to see the effect of the catalyst.

Refluxing of a mixture of mesityl oxide with benzoylacetone in heptane-benzene (1:1) in a Dean-Stark apparatus for 60 h yielded a brown crystalline mass. Most of the unreacted benzoylacetone was removed by repeated fractional crystallisation and separation of the three reaction products was achieved by a combination of column-and-preparative tlc technique. They were identified as 4-acetyl-5,5-dimethyl-3-phenylcyclohex-2-enone (3), 4-benzoyl-3,5,5-trimethylcyclohex-2-enone (4) and 6-benzoyl-3,5,5-trimethylcyclohex-2-enone (5), the yields being 10, 8 and 6%, respectively, on the basis of benzoylacetone consumed. The presence of carbonyl groups in these compounds was confirmed by converting them to their respective 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazones. Compounds 3, 4 and 5 responded to the usual tests for unsaturation with bromine in CCl_4 and potassium permanganate solution. The *gem*-dimethyl groups appeared as separate 3H singlets (δ 1.17 and 1.56 for 3, 1.05 and 1.12 for 4 and

for $\text{O}=\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$ in 3, 2.0 for $=\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$ in 4, 1.85 for $=\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$ in 5) as expected. Their methine proton exhibited 1H singlet at δ 4.5, 4.27 and 4.19. The non-equivalent methylene protons of 3, 4 and 5 appeared as doublets at δ 2.00 and 2.47 (J 1.60Hz), 1.05 and 2.90 (J 16.0Hz) and 1.85 and 2.03 (J 15.5Hz), respectively. The vinylic protons of 3, 4 and 5 were readily noted at δ 5.53, 5.89 and 6.0. The aromatic protons of the three isomers 3, 4 and 5 appeared as sets of complex multiplet, around δ 7.50 and 7.93, 7.50 and 7.95, and 7.59 and 8.05, respectively. The ir, uv and nmr spectra of 3, 4 and 5 are almost similar and could not distinguish amongst the three structures. The mass spectra, however, were helpful in overcoming this problem. Compounds 3, 4 and 5 showed the pseudo-molecular ion peak at m/z 243 ($M+1$) and corresponded to the molecular formula $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2$. The mass fragmentation pattern of 4 and 5 was similar but different from that of 3. The mass fragments of m/z 227 and 199 in 3 are easily explained by loss of CH_3 and CO of the acyl group from the parent ion. The presence of acyl cation group in 3 was further evidenced by the acylium (m/z 43) mass peak. Compounds 4 and 5 showed peaks at m/z 137, 105, 77 and 65 besides that at 243 (and 242 for 5). The base peak at m/z 105 was for the benzoyl cation which further eliminated a CO molecule to give the intense peak at m/z 77. The mass spectra, however, failed to distinguish between 4 and 5. However, the ir spectra of 5 provided a clue for the distinction. It showed a moderate broad hydroxyl absorption over the range $3\ 220-3\ 605\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ which is expected from the enol form of the 1,3-diketone structure (5). The ir spectra of 4 did not show any such absorption in this region. Condensation of mesityl oxide with benzoyl acetone in the presence of anhydrous AlCl_3 , yielded 4 and two other compounds which could not be characterised.

Compounds 3, 4 and 5 appear to be unreported in the literature, however an isomer of these compounds, 2-benzoyl-3,5,5-trimethylcyclohex-2-enone was synthesised through a different route¹⁵.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected and were determined on a Gallenkamp melting point apparatus. Electronic spectra were measured on a Beckman ACOTT CIII spectrophotometer in absolute alcohol, and infrared spectra on a Beckman IR 4220 spectrophotometer. Nmr spectra were recorded in CDCl_3 on a 50 MHz spectrophotometer with TMS as internal standard and mass spectra on a DS-50 spectrometer at the Chemistry Department of Queen Elizabeth College, London.

Reaction of mesityl oxide with benzoylacetone catalysed by anhydrous zinc chloride: A mixture of mesityl oxide (16.4 g, 0.17 mol), benzoyl acetone (27 g, 0.17 mol), anhydrous zinc chloride (3.4 g, 0.026 mol), heptane (30 ml) and benzene (30 ml)

0.94 and 1.16 for 5). Their third methyl group also gave rise to singlets but at lower fields (δ 1.8

was refluxed for 60 h in a Dean—Stark apparatus. The cooled reaction mixture was successively washed with distilled water, 5% sodium bicarbonate and distilled water. The organic layer was dried (anhydrous Na_2SO_4), filtered and the solvent removed to yield a deep brown crystalline residue. Most of the unreacted benzoyl acetone was removed by fractional crystallisation from petroleum ether. The mother liquor was evaporated to dryness to yield a crude material (70 g).

Separation of 3, 4 and 5: By column chromatography: The crude material (500 mg) was chromatographed on silica gel (60–120 mesh, B D H) and eluted with petroleum ether—ethyl acetate (9:1). The process separated among others, the unreacted benzoyl acetone (250 mg) and the titled cyclohexenones, 3 (12 mg) and 4 (9 mg) as yellowish viscous liquid, while the isomer 5 (6 mg) as a deep brown semi-solid.

By preparative tlc: The crude reaction product (500 mg) was resolved by preparative tlc in petroleum ether—ethyl acetate (9:1) into 3 (R_f 0.77), 4 (R_f 0.40) and 5 (R_f 0.14), their yields being 10, 8 and 6%, respectively, and benzoylacetone.

4-Acetyl-5,5 dimethyl-3-phenylcyclohex-2-enone (3): It showed ν_{max} (neat) 1705 ($\text{CO}-\text{CH}_3$), 1650 (α,β -unsaturated-ketone), 1575, 1550 (ph. gr.), 175, 1350 cm^{-1} (gem dimethyl); λ_{max} (EtOH) 248 nm; δ 1.17 (3H) and 1.56 (3H) (gem-dimethyl), 1.82 (3H, $-\text{CO}-\text{CH}_3$), 2.00 (1H, d) and 2.47 (1H, d) (J 16.0 Hz, methylene protons), 4.50 (1H, CH), 5.53 (1H, =CH) and 7.53–7.93 (5H, m, ArH); m/z 243 ($M+1$) (5%), 227(100%), 199(3%), 185(5%), 105 (43%), 77(35%) and 43(18%); 2,4-DNP (m.p. 128–30°).

4-Benzoyl-3,5,5-trimethylcyclohex-2-enone (4): It showed ν_{max} (neat) 1655 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1590, 1575 (ph. gr.), 1365, 1330 cm^{-1} (gem-dimethyl); λ_{max} (EtOH) 246 nm; δ 1.05 (3H) and 1.12 (3H) (gem-dimethyl), 2.00 (3H, = CCH_3), 1.95 (1H, d) and 2.90 (1H, d) (J 16.0 Hz, methylene protons), 4.27 (1H, CH), 5.89 (1H, =CH), 7.54–7.95 (5H, m, ArH); m/z 243 ($M+1$) (14%), 227(6%), 137(4%), 105(100%), 77(10%) and 65(2%); 2,4-DNP (m.p. 124–26°).

6-Benzoyl-3,5,5-trimethylcyclohex-2-enone (5): It showed ν_{max} (neat) 1655 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1592, 1575 (ph. ring), 1370, 1335 cm^{-1} (gem-dimethyl); λ_{max} (EtOH) 250 nm; δ 0.94 (3H) and 1.16 (3H) (gem-dimethyl), 1.85 (3H, = CCH_3), 2.03 (1H, d) and 2.85 (1H, d) (J 15.5 Hz, methylene protons), 4.19 (1H, CH), 6.0 (1H, =CH), 7.90–8.04 (5H, m, ArH); m/z 243 ($M+1$) (10%), 227(3%), 137(3%), 105 (100%), 77(70%) and 65(4%); 2,4-DNP (m.p. 121–23°).

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Fragmentation Pathways in the Mass Spectra of 2-Methylisoflavone Derivatives. Useful in their Diagnosis

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ISOFLAVONES, an important group of natural products, occur widely in the plant kingdom and many of them possess oestrogenic, antitumoral and insecticidal properties^{1,2}. 2-Methylisoflavones are now coming into prominence as the first examples of their occurrence in plants have been reported^{3,4} in recent years only. These compounds seem to be important also because they are almost twice as toxic as the corresponding 2-substituted-isoflavones⁵. No detailed record of the mass spectral fragmentation of the natural analogues (hydroxy or methoxy substituted) of 2-methylisoflavones has been published so far. We have earlier reported⁶ the fragmentation pattern of the synthetic samples of a few acetyl and allyl substituted derivatives. The present paper discusses the results of the mass spectrometric investigations of seven differently substituted 2-methylisoflavones and the utility of these studies in the structure elucidation of this important class of compounds.

The isoflavones (1–7) used in this study were purified by preparative tlc and/or crystallisation, and the purity was $\geq 99\%$. The low resolution electron impact mass spectra of all the seven samples were carried out with a Swedish LKB instrument of the USSR Academy of Sciences, Moscow. Mass spectra were recorded by direct insertion with the inlet temperatures maintained between 40 and 70°, and an electron energy of 70 eV.